

Evaluation of nursing interns' portfolio and faculty raters' satisfaction

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Abstract: Background: Many performance tests and tools as portfolio directly measure learning processes and products and are recommended in nursing education. Aim of the study was to evaluate the nursing interns' portfolio and satisfaction of faculty raters. Subjects and methods: Descriptive design was used to conduct the present study. Setting: This study was conducted at Faculty of Nursing at Suez Canal University Sample: Faculty raters (N= 9) and nursing interns' portfolio (N= 100). Tools of data collection: Data was collected using two tools through study phases, Rating scales with scoring rubrics; Questionnaire sheet to the faculty raters about their satisfaction of the developed portfolio. Results: All of the nursing interns fulfill all requirements of the portfolio and discuss portfolio with their supervisors. The median score of all portfolio evaluation elements are 4 which indicate excellent score except working in the development according to community needs and reflection on all activity scored 3 which indicate very good score. All faculty raters (100%) were highly satisfied on the developed portfolio except portfolio assessment that is difficult was 66.7%. Conclusion: The nursing interns' portfolio is evaluated by faculty raters as an excellent portfolio and having a high level of satisfaction. Recommendation: conducting regular training program to the faculty raters about and how to use it. Establishing a system for analyzing and using the data obtained from nursing interns' portfolios evaluation for improving the nursing interns' achievement.

Keywords: Internship, nursing interns' portfolio and faculty raters' satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Internship program is a kind of practical learning in which students apply the knowledge they have learned in the academic study. Internship program is important for students as they will be able to integrate intellectual skills in real life situation, enhance critical thinking ability, communication, and better occupational capability (Lam & Ching, 2007); (Sarlan et al., 2008). Students' development in the internship needs their performance to be observed and assessed (Zakaria, 2016). Observing students' portfolio during the internship is considered one of the effective attempts to monitor students' tasks in internship program (Neades, 2003). Portfolio is a set of evidences and documents which show that learning is occurring. (Hekmatpou, 2013). Also, it is applied as an approach for integration of theory and practice and developing the nursing profession (McMullan, 2008). It has been used as a method for demonstrating nursing competency (Mills, 2009) and (Latifi et al., 2011).

It is used to show students' learning, monitor their progress and to motivate them at excellent levels through summative and formative evaluation (Haverkamp & Vogt, 2015).

Portfolios provide successful feedback sessions by counting checkpoints in an education period. It is a harmony of meeting regularly to debate what's going well, problem areas and the way the learner is seen by the colleagues. Otherwise, facilitators will offer feedback for each step the learner performs in the clinical setting. Consequently, it is done as a proof to reflect upon their strengths and weaknesses (Michos et al., 2022).

Significance of the study:

Portfolio is an excellent tool for education and evaluation. Despite proper documentation about the use of portfolios in evaluating nursing students and inadequate study on the effectiveness of this method, for various reasons such as ignorance, lack of consensus on the benefits of using this method, this study is aiming at evaluating the nursing interns' portfolio and satisfaction of faculty raters regarding portfolio

The aim of the study: The current study aims to evaluate the nursing interns' portfolio and satisfaction of faculty raters

II. SUBJECTS AND METHODS

Study design: Descriptive research design was adopted to conduct this study.

The sample of the study: Faculty raters (N= 9) and nursing intern's portfolio (N= 100).

Study setting: Faculty of Nursing at Suez Canal University

Tools of data collection:**Tool 1: Rating scales with scoring rubrics**

This tool was adopted from El-Araby et al. (2012) and the needed modification was done by the researcher. This tool was used for portfolio assessment it contains (14) questions divided into two parts: quality of portfolio and general evaluation. The quality of portfolio includes (12) items: (10 items) cover the nursing interns' activities in portfolio, (2 items) cover the reflections on activities and portfolio ILOs achievement. Whereas the general evaluation includes (2 items) cover fulfilling all requirements of portfolio and discussing it with supervisors. Along with 4 points rating scale, the scale was excellent (8.5-10/10), very good (7.5-<8.5/10), satisfactory (6-<7.5/10) and unsatisfactory (<6/10)). This scale was including a scoring rubric, which provided a description of each score.

Tool 2: Faculty raters' satisfaction questionnaire sheet

This tool was adopted from El-Araby et al. (2012) and used to ask about faculty raters' satisfaction of the developed portfolio regarding provision of helpful information (7 items) and using portfolio as an evaluation tool (7 items). The faculty raters' satisfaction regarding the developed portfolio was measured on a 5 points likert scale ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). This scale was converted into three levels: low satisfaction (1-2), moderate satisfaction (3) and high satisfaction (4-5).

Reliability and validity:

Cronbach's Coefficient Alpha was calculated to assess the reliability of the tools that used throughout the study. It was ranged: from 74-80% with total score 81% for faculty raters' satisfaction questionnaire tool and from 68-86% with total score 84% for rating scales with scoring rubrics tool compared with 70% for the original tool. The tools of data collection had been checked for its content validity by academic staff from different faculties of nursing.

Field work:

The fulfilled portfolios by nursing interns were evaluated after ending their internship year by the faculty raters, followed by measuring faculty raters' satisfaction regarding nursing interns' Portfolio which takes 25 minutes for fulfillment. The faculty raters divided into two groups, the researcher accompanied in the two groups and the implemented portfolio distributed on them. Each portfolio corrected 5 times by faculty raters for more assurance of portfolio evaluation.

NB: All of the faculty raters were given the same instructions. The researcher met personally each of them. Before distributing the questionnaire sheets, the purpose of the study and the components of the tools were explained to the participants. The data were collected through meeting the faculty raters in their work setting. The researcher checked each

questionnaire sheet after the participant completed it to ensure the absence of any missing information. This phase taking two months (from beginning of November 2019 to the end of December 2019).

Administrative design:

Official permission it was obtained from the Dean of the faculty and Vice Dean for Community Service and Environmental Affairs for data collection from faculty raters of faculty of nursing/ Suez Canal University,

Ethical considerations:

Agreement of all participants was obtained after explanation about the nature of the study and its aim.

Any individual included in the study was informed that he/she has the right to refuse to participate in the study or withdraw from the study at any time with no negative consequences to them. Also, the confidentiality of the data and results was maintained.

Statistical design:

Data were coded and analyzed using SPSS package version 20.

Kolmogorov – Smirnov test was used to examine the normality of data distribution and the data was nonparametric data.

Descriptive statistics including frequency, distribution, mean and standard deviation were used to describe different characteristics and variables of the study.

Table (1): Description of socio-demographic characteristics of the faculty raters (N=9).

The socio-demographic data		Sample size (n=9)	
		No.	%
Age groups	25-29 Y	3	33.33
	30-37 Y	6	66.67
	Mean±SD	30.56±3.97	
Gender	Male	0	0.00
	Female	9	100.00
Academic degree	Demonstrator	3	33.33
	Assistant lecture	4	44.44
	lecture	2	22.22
Nursing Specialty	Administration	2	22.22
	Obstetrics and gynecology	2	22.22
	Medical & surgical	2	22.22
	Community health	2	22.22
	Pediatric	1	11.11
Years of experiences	3 months	3	33.33
	1 y	1	11.11
	2y	2	22.22
	3y	1	11.11
	8y	1	11.11
	10y	1	11.11
	Mean±SD	2.97±3.58	

Table (1) reveal description of socio-demographic characteristics of the faculty raters. It was found that more than half (66.67%) of faculty raters aged about thirty to thirty seven years and only 33.33% aged twenty five to twenty nine years. Regarding the gender of the faculty raters, all of them (100 %) were females, 44.44% of them were assistant lectures while 22.22% were lectures. In addition, the faculty raters had different nursing specialties which were Nursing Administration, Obstetrics & Gynecology, Medical & Surgical nursing, Community Health Nursing and Pediatric Nursing. They had experiences in internship supervision ranged from 10 years to 3 months of experiences.

Table (2): General evaluation of Nursing Interns' Portfolio (N=500 views).

The student does the following:	Yes		No	
	No.	%	No.	%
Fulfill all requirements of portfolio	500	100.00	0	00.00
Discuss portfolio with supervisor	500	100.00	0	00.00
Average	500	100	0	0

Table (2) show general evaluation of Nursing Interns' Portfolio. It was found that all of the nursing interns fulfilling all requirements of the portfolio and discussing portfolio with their supervisors.

Table (3): Median of Nursing Interns' Portfolio evaluation (N=500 views).

Portfolio Elements	Median
The student does the following:	
Nursing care needs	4
High quality nursing care	4
Health education	4
Work in the development according to community needs	3
Self-evaluation (strengths points)	4
Self-evaluation (weakness points)	4
Attending workshops	4
Administration sheets	4
Presentation or case study	4
Nursing activities	4
Reflects on all activity	3
The student does the ILOs	4
Total	4

Table (3) illustrate median of Nursing Interns' Portfolio evaluation score. It was found that all median score of portfolio evaluation are 4 which indicates excellent score except in work in the development according to community needs and reflects on all activity were 3 which indicates very good score.

Table (4): Median of Faculty Raters' Satisfaction regarding Nursing Interns' Portfolio (N=9).

Satisfaction assessment	Median
Provision with helpful information about	
ILOs	5
Presentation	5
Case study	5
Activity report	5
Nursing care plan	5
Health education session	5
Achieved ILOs	5
Portfolio as an evaluation tool	
Combination of clinical and portfolio	5
Portfolio assess strengths and weakness	5
Agreement with allocation of students into excellent, very good, satisfactory, unsatisfactory	5
Instructions for examiners were clear	5
Pleased at standard achieved by examination students	5
Portfolio assessment is difficult	2
Recommend same portfolio in subsequent years	5
Overall faculty raters satisfaction assessment	5

Table (4) shows median of Faculty Raters' Satisfaction regarding Nursing Interns' Portfolio. It was found that median of faculty raters' satisfaction is 5 which indicates to highly level of satisfaction.

III. DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Concerning socio-demographic characteristics of the faculty raters, the current study revealed that more than half of the faculty raters were in age about thirty to thirty seven years, all of them were females, and about one third was assistant lectures with 3 months experiences in internship. This result was in agreement with (Bramley et al., 2021) who studied the design, implementation and evaluation of novel work-based clinical assessment tool (portfolio) and found that majority of faculty raters were female. This in addition to (Chang, 2018) who studied the undergraduate student nurses' functional requirements for portfolios, and found that half of faculty raters were assistant lecturer and had experience with internship more than six months.

Regarding general evaluation of Nursing Interns' Portfolio, the current study found that all of the nursing interns filling all requirements of the portfolio and discussing portfolio with their supervisors. This result may be due to training program help nursing interns' student about understood portfolio and enhance their performance during internship period.

This result was supported with (Schiele et al., 2017) who studied the using portfolios to demonstrate high-impact educational practices and promote student employment success, and found that majority of students' filled portfolio and discussed portfolio with their supervisors. Also, (Douglas et al., 2019) that studied the college students' motivation and confidence for portfolio use and found that majority of students had improvement of their performance with using of portfolio. Whereas (Payne et al., 2020) who studied the student perceptions about the production of portfolios, and found that more than half of students could fill portfolio correctly.

In regarding to median of Nursing Interns' Portfolio evaluation score, the current study found that all median score of portfolio evaluation were excellent except in work in the development according to community needs and reflects on all activity were very good. This result was in agreement with (Scully et al., 2018) who studied the learning portfolio in higher education, and found that all median score of portfolio evaluation were excellent

Concerning levels of Faculty Rater's Satisfaction about the Nursing Interns' Portfolio, the current study found that all of the faculty raters were highly satisfied in developed portfolio. This result was accordance with (Hansen & Dohn, 2018) who studied the design principles for designing simulated social practices, and found that majority of faculty raters had high level of satisfaction about developed portfolio. On the other hand, (Chang, 2018) who studied the undergraduate student nurses' functional requirements for portfolios found that half of faculty raters had low level of satisfaction about developed portfolio.

Regarding median of Faculty Rater's Satisfaction regarding Nursing Interns' Portfolio, the current study found that median of faculty raters satisfaction is a high score with the developed portfolio which indicates to high level of satisfaction. This result was in agreement with (Beckers et al., 2021) who studied the facilitating self-directed learning skills and motivation with a development portfolio, and found that median of faculty raters satisfaction is a high score with the developed portfolio. Also, this result is supported by (Bramley et al., 2021) who found that majority of faculty raters were satisfied about developed portfolio.

Conclusion

Based on the finding of the current study, it was concluded that the developed Nursing Interns' Portfolio is evaluated as an excellent portfolio with a high level of satisfaction by faculty raters from different nursing specialties.

Recommendations

In the light of the study findings, can be recommended with conducting regular training program to the faculty raters about and how to use it. Establishing a system for analyzing and using the data obtained from the reviewing nursing interns' portfolios for improving the nursing interns' achievement.

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